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Relationship Between Experiential Learning, Emotional Intelligence And Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Among Business Education Students In Tertiary Institutions In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated relationship between experiential learning, emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. Six research questions were raised and three hypotheses were equally formulated in line with the specific objectives of the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Several literature were reviewed for the study along with the theoretical framework to explain the facts generated in the study. Situated Learning Theory by Jean Lave in 1988 was adopted. The correlational survey design was utilized in this study. Population of the study was 577 business Education students from tertiary institutions in Delta State. The sample size was 173, hence, the sampling technique adopted was simple random sampling technique. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. Pearson's coefficient of determination was used to answer the research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and, multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between experiential learning and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Also, that there was a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. It was further revealed that emotional intelligence is a better predictor of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State than experiential learning among others. The study recommended that University management should ensure that SIWES training remain a mandatory component of university education. Also, that Business education lecturers should ensure that students are engaged in hands-on training and ensure that marks are awarded to students in such trainings to encourage students to fully participate in such programmes. Similarly, Business education students should endeavour to develop their emotional intelligence quotient such as self-awareness, self-regulation and social skills as it helps in acquisition of entrepreneurial skills among students.

Keywords: Business education, students, emotional intelligence, entrepreneurial skills

INTRODUCTION

There is no gain saying the fact that education in Nigeria has been adopted as an essential element for growth, progress and national development economically, socially and politically. It directly contributes to the growth of national economy by improving the skills and productive capacity of citizens. This is why we can hardly see any industrialized country without a well-developed education and training system, a system that not only provides a rich variety of programmes or courses that respond to both personal and national development, but also seeks to remove barriers to learners' participation. These industrialized countries make heavy investments on education and training because of the roles that knowledge and skills play in modern economy. This modern economy emphasizes knowledge, skill acquisition and technology which are imperative to the nation's development.

Skill acquisition is defined as the ability to be trained on a particular task or function (Mike, 2014). Mike emphasized that the importance of skill acquisition includes self-employment, diverse job opportunities, employment generation, effective function, and crime reduction. Idoko as cited in Nyemaekile and Adiele (2022) defined skill acquisition as the form of training by individuals or group of individuals that can lead to acquisition of knowledge for self-sustenance. It involves the training of people in different fields of trade under a legal agreement between the trainers and the trainees for certain duration and under certain conditions. Equipping business education postgraduates' students with different skills are means of taking corrective measure for the high level of unemployment. Without skill acquisition the national goals of employment generation and self-sustainability cannot be realized hence, corruption and violence will rise to high level.

Entrepreneurship skills are dynamic social skills needed to be successful entrepreneurs. These skills make individuals to become successful entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers. The skills enable individuals, solely or in collaboration with others to identify possibilities and utilize them to transform ideas into practical and goal-oriented activities in a social, cultural or economic context. Entrepreneurship skills involve a range of attributes, such as creativity, team work, risk management, and ability to handle uncertainty in a business venture. Gomez et al. (2023) identified leadership, negotiation, creative thinking, exposure to technology, opportunity identification, idea generation and protection, tolerance, ability to tackle challenges at different entrepreneurial stages, ability to write and communicate business plans, new venture development, ability to diagnose business performance, networking and mentorship, environmental analysis, computer and simulation skills, invention and innovation as entrepreneurship skills. At the tertiary institution level, several courses are offered to equip students with entrepreneurial skills. One of such courses is Business Education.

Business education is that part of vocational and technology education programme that provides the necessary business, economic, education knowledge, skills and competencies needed to teach business subjects in secondary schools, colleges and universities (Udo, 2016). Business education is a course that prepares students to improve on the jobs or in business and equally prepares them to manage their own business affairs and to function intelligently as consumers and citizens in a business economy (Anorue & Madu, 2020). The objectives of Business Education programme include to develop basic skills for personal use in the future, to acquire the basic knowledge and skills of business education; to relate the knowledge and skills acquired to national development; to develop basic skills in office occupation; to provide the needed background for teaching in business subject; to prepare students or further training in business studies; to provide orientation and basic skills with which to start a life of work for those who may not undergo further training. This implies that well cherished objectives of business education cannot be achieved if emphasis is not laid on importance of entrepreneurship skill acquisition while implementing curriculum at the tertiary education level. Therefore, through development of entrepreneurship skills, all these objectives could be achieved for sustainability. Business education prepares individuals for gainful employment and workable livelihood as well as development in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes (Saidu, Dahiru & Suleiman, 2017). Entrepreneurship Education is one of the components of Business education (Udo, 2016). It is pertinent to note that individuals' activities that convert ideas into economic opportunities lie at the middle of entrepreneurship (Afolabi, 2015).

Despite the position of entrepreneurship to the Business Education Programme, interaction with most graduates of tertiary institutions revealed that curriculum implementation tends to inadequately equip them with the intricacies of managing across the range of functions in business organisation. The landscapes that will lead to realization of the objectives of entrepreneurial education are not translated into practical realities during the process of policy implementation. This probably explained why Adamu as cited in Adeyemi and Adeyemo, (2023) lamented that, most university graduates lack skills to work across boundaries on complex, interrelated problems needed for successful entrepreneurship. These have affected the expansion of pool of entrepreneurial talent needed to develop and manage new business ventures upon graduation in Nigeria. As a result, massive undergraduates are waiting for white collar jobs rather than starting their businesses for their self-reliance which led to increase in the rate of unemployment in the country.

The nature of entrepreneurship education given to students in Nigerian universities gives room for concern. There is general complain of inadequate funding, poor state of infrastructure in universities and dearth of experienced entrepreneurship teachers that will cope with the challenges of the new curriculum. All these affect the realization of the objectives of entrepreneurial education. According to Business Day, (2024), the state of funding and infrastructure in the Nigerian university system is embarrassing. The focus of this study is on the relationship between experiential learning, emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skill acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

Experiential learning is a hands-on, collaborative, and immersive learning style that consist of direct experience and reflection. It is a learning method that concedes individuals to learn by doing, rather than merely listening or reading. In other words, experiential learning, as an educational approach, transforms the traditional classroom setting by placing a strong emphasis on practical, hands-on experiences. Experiential learning can take different forms, such as: internships/student industrial work experience scheme, project-based learning, field trips, simulations, service-learning projects, games, role-playing and hands-on training. In the realm of business education, this methodology may become a powerful catalyst for the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills among students. Rather than relying solely on theoretical instruction, experiential learning immerses students in real-world scenarios, fostering a more profound understanding of entrepreneurial principles. Through this approach, business education students are encouraged to actively apply theoretical knowledge to authentic business challenges, bridging the gap between academic concepts and practical implementation. This engagement cultivates critical thinking as students grapple with real problems, make decisions, and adapt to uncertainties – skills crucial for aspiring entrepreneurs navigating the complexities of the business world.

Experiential learning plays a pivotal role in shaping the entrepreneurial mind-set among students, equipping them with essential skills and fostering a proactive approach to business challenges. This learning approach not only helps students take calculated risks and make decisions in ambiguous situations—mirroring the real-world challenges faced by entrepreneurs—but also emphasizes teamwork and communication skills through collaborative projects (Kolb, 2015). Such experiences reflect the collaborative nature of entrepreneurial ventures, enhancing students' ability to work effectively in teams.

Moreover, experiential learning cultivates an entrepreneurial mind-set by engaging students in creative problem-solving and teaching resilience in the face of setbacks. Students learn to navigate challenges innovatively, which is crucial for success in the ever-evolving business landscape (Beckman, 2023). Networking opportunities with industry professionals provide valuable insights and potential pathways for future entrepreneurial endeavours, reinforcing the practical application of classroom knowledge (Rae, 2022).

Internship or student industrial work experience scheme (SIWES) is basically a type of temporary work experience that offer students or young graduates with the opportunity to gain practical skills and knowledge in a professional setting or particular industry. SIWES is a skill training program designed to expose and prepare students of tertiary institutions for industrial work situation they are likely to meet after graduation by providing these students with the opportunity to become familiar with and gain experience in handling equipment and machinery that are typically unavailable in their institutions of

higher learning (Akpojotor, 2023). Internship or SIWES provide hands-on experience, allowing individuals to apply classroom knowledge to real-world situations. It offer chances of developing and refining relevant skills to industry or career path. This experiential learning help in facilitating career exploration and development. It enable the acquisition of new skills and the enhancement of existing ones.

Another type of experiential learning is Hands-on training. In this learning style, individual learn by directly participating in activities, exercises, or projects. It involves practical, hands-on experience with equipment, tools, or software, allowing learners to develop skills and knowledge through direct application. Hands-on training could be in form of workshop, simulations, apprenticeships, project-based learning or on-the-job training. These hands-on training may provide learners with practical experiences, develop skills, and prepares them for real-world scenarios.

Further, simulation is another technique used to imitate real-world settings, situations, scenarios or environments in a controlled and safe manner. Under this experiential learning method, learners are allowed to practice, develop skills, and make mistakes without consequences. There are various types of simulations like computer-based simulations, physical simulations and hybrid simulations.

However, the reflective aspect of experiential learning encourages students to analyze their experiences, extract meaningful lessons, and apply these insights to future situations (Moon, 2013). This reflective process contributes to a continuous learning cycle, fostering adaptability and a growth mindset - qualities integral to entrepreneurial success. In essence, experiential learning in business education serves as a dynamic medium for students to not only comprehend entrepreneurial concepts but to embody them through active participation in entrepreneurial activities.

Emotional intelligence (EI) refers to the ability to recognize and understand emotions in oneself and others, and to use this awareness to guide thought and behaviour. However, EI is another key component in the development of entrepreneurial skills among students. EI encompasses self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, motivation, empathy and relationship management, all of which are vital in the context of entrepreneurship (Sadiku et al., 2020). Students with high EI can discern their motivations and values, aligning their entrepreneurial pursuits with personal goals.

One of the key component of EI is self-awareness which is the ability to have a clear and honest understanding of one's own thoughts, feelings, strengths, weaknesses, values, and motivations. It involves being aware of one's emotions, attitudes, and behaviours, and how they impact one's relationships and interactions with that of other people. This self-awareness is foundational for effective self-regulation, enabling students to manage high-pressure situations and uncertainties inherent in entrepreneurship (Ristovska & Blazheska, 2021).

In order for business education students to acquire entrepreneurial skill they may require certain level of self-regulation. Self-regulation refers to the ability to control and manage one's own thoughts, feelings, and behaviours in order to achieve goals, meet expectations, and maintain a sense of well-being. It involves being able to regulate one's own emotions, motivation, and behaviour in the face of challenges, stress, or adversity. In other words, it is the capacity or ability to control one's own thoughts, emotions and actions. Hence, self-regulation is a vital process that allows people to behave adequately, carry out tasks properly, and abstain from activities that may be harmful to their own livelihood (Baumeister & Heatherton, 1996 in Fuente et al. (2014).

Another component of EI is social skills which refers to the abilities and strategies used to interact and communicate effectively with others, build and maintain relationships, and navigate social situations. These skills are essential for personal and professional success, as they enable individuals to form connections, collaborate, and achieve common goal. Social skills involve patterns of behaviour that support successful social relationships and enable individual to work efficiently with others (Triyanti, 2023). Low social skills can be a disadvantage by harming personal learning achievement. Therefore, the ability to develop social skills is one of the assets owned by students, which allows them to interact with others during the learning process (Green et al., 2021). These social skills may assist students to acquire entrepreneurial skills

Motivation and passion, essential for entrepreneurial success, are significantly enhanced by emotional intelligence. Students competent in EI are better at setting meaningful goals, remaining committed to their objectives, and channelling enthusiasm into their entrepreneurial endeavours (Sosik et al., 2019). Empathy, a dimension of EI, enhances communication and collaboration skills, which are invaluable in customer relations and team dynamics within the entrepreneurial landscape.

Furthermore, adaptability is a crucial trait for entrepreneurs as it may influenced emotional intelligence. It is believed that Individuals with high EI navigate change effectively, learn from experiences, and adjust strategies based on feedback and market dynamics. Also, leadership qualities essential for entrepreneurship are enhanced through EI, enabling individuals to inspire and build trust within their teams and networks (Pomona Chamber of Commerce, 2023). Based on the aforementioned, the researcher decide to carry out a study on relationship between experiential learning, emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Business education graduates in Delta State frequently encounter the challenge of unemployment, and their businesses often face failure within the initial five years of operation due to a lack of acquired entrepreneurial skills. It becomes particularly disheartening and discouraging when an entrepreneur, who has endured long periods of unemployment before initiating their own business, is compelled to cease operations due to insufficient entrepreneurial skills. The tertiary institutions in Delta State consistently produce graduates who struggle to achieve self-sustainability in running their businesses, primarily due to a deficiency in high-level entrepreneurial skills. The incorporation of entrepreneurship education in business programs across tertiary institutions in the state is intended to address this gap and equip business education graduates with the necessary entrepreneurial skills.

Despite the endeavours to empower business education graduates in Delta State with entrepreneurial skills, many operators of Small-Scale Enterprises (SMEs) continue to face challenges in effectively managing their businesses. Numerous studies have explored entrepreneurial skill acquisition using varied concepts and constructs. However, to our knowledge, there appears to be a scarcity of empirical research specifically investigating the influence of experiential learning and emotional intelligence on the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills among students in tertiary institutions. In view of this, the problem of this study, is, to determine the relationship between experiential learning, emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between SIWES and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
2. What is the relationship between hands-on training and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
3. What is the relationship between simulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
4. What is the relationship between self-awareness and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
5. What is the relationship between self-regulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
6. What is the relationship between social skills and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

1.4 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between experiential learning, emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. The study specifically examined the:

1. Relationship between SIWES and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

2. Relationship between hands-on training and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
3. Relationship between simulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
4. Relationship between self-awareness and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
5. Relationship between self-regulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
6. Relationship between social-skills and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

1.5 **Hypotheses**

The following hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between experiential learning and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
3. Experiential learning is a better predictor of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State than emotional intelligence.

1.6 **Significance of the Study**

The outcome of this study will be very useful to policy makers, business education lecturers, students and other researchers

Policy makers will find the outcome of this study very useful since it will provide information that will enhance development of policies and initiatives aimed at enhancing entrepreneurship education and fostering a more conducive environment for skill development among students. Insights from the study can guide policymakers in formulating curriculum policies that prioritize experiential learning methodologies within the Business Education framework. Understanding how hands-on experiences contribute to entrepreneurial skill acquisition allows policymakers to advocate for and implement curriculum reforms that integrate practical learning opportunities, ensuring alignment with the dynamic needs of the entrepreneurial landscape. Moreover, the study's revelations on the role of emotional intelligence in shaping entrepreneurial skills can influence policies related to both teacher training and student support systems. Policymakers can consider incorporating training programs for educators that emphasize the cultivation of emotional intelligence among students. Additionally, policies promoting initiatives such as counselling services or workshops focused on emotional intelligence can be implemented to create a supportive learning environment that nurtures the socio-emotional aspects crucial for entrepreneurial success. Business Education lecturers can equally benefit from the outcome of the study in several ways. For instance, it can serve as a guide for lecturers in refining their teaching approaches and enriching the learning experiences they provide to students. Understanding how experiential learning contributes to entrepreneurial skill development enables lecturers to tailor their instructional methods. They can incorporate more practical and hands-on activities, case studies, and real-world projects into their curriculum. This approach not only aligns with the findings of the study but also enhances student engagement by offering a more dynamic and applied learning environment. Insights into the role of emotional intelligence in entrepreneurial skill acquisition empower lecturers to focus on socio-emotional aspects in their teaching. Lecturers can integrate activities and discussions that encourage students to reflect on and develop their emotional intelligence. This may involve incorporating scenarios that simulate real-world entrepreneurial challenges, fostering self-awareness, and promoting interpersonal skills.

The outcome of the study will also be of great benefit to students. Such a study can significantly enhance the overall educational experience by directly impacting their skill development, mindset, and readiness for the dynamic world of entrepreneurship. Understanding the influence of experiential learning allows students to engage in practical, real-world applications of theoretical concepts. This hands-on approach

not only reinforces their understanding of entrepreneurship but also equips them with practical skills that go beyond traditional classroom learning. Students can actively participate in simulated business scenarios, projects, and case studies, fostering a deeper appreciation for the complexities of entrepreneurial endeavours. Insights into the role of emotional intelligence provide students with a heightened awareness of the socio-emotional aspects critical for entrepreneurial success. By emphasizing self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and interpersonal skills, students can develop a well-rounded set of abilities that are invaluable in the entrepreneurial landscape. This understanding encourages a holistic approach to skill acquisition, emphasizing not only technical competencies but also the emotional intelligence necessary for effective leadership and collaboration.

Other researchers can also benefit from the outcome of the study. The insights gained from the study can contribute to the existing body of knowledge, inspire further research endeavours, and inform the design of future studies in entrepreneurship education. The study's findings can serve as a valuable reference for researchers interested in understanding the effectiveness of experiential learning in the context of entrepreneurship education. By providing empirical evidence on the impact of hands-on experiences, the study contributes to the scholarly discourse on pedagogical approaches within business education. Other researchers can use this foundation to explore other aspects of experiential learning or to conduct comparative studies across different educational settings in other regions. The exploration of emotional intelligence's role in entrepreneurial skill acquisition adds a novel dimension to the existing literature. Researchers in related fields, such as psychology, education, and organizational behaviour, may find the study's insights valuable for understanding the intersection of emotional intelligence and entrepreneurship. This interdisciplinary perspective can stimulate collaborative research efforts and open avenues for cross-disciplinary investigations into the socio-emotional aspects of skill development.

1.7 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The geographical scope of the study covered public tertiary institutions offering business education programme in Delta State. While the content variable covered experiential learning, emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skill acquisition. Under the experiential learning which is an independent variable, we have SIWES, hands-on training and simulation. Further, under the emotional intelligence which is another independent variable, we have self-awareness, self-regulation and social-skills. The study will be delimited to only Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter dealt with the research methods and procedures used in the study. The chapter addressed the following sub-headings: Research Design, Population of the Study, Sample and Sampling, Research Instruments, Validity of the Research Instrument, Reliability of the Research Instrument, Method of Data Collection, and Method of Data Analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted the correlational research design. This enabled the researcher to examine relationship between experiential learning, emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. The use of correlational research design is based on the fact that the design is used to determine the relationship that exists between two or more variables (Abdullah, et al., 2019).

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population of the study was year 2 or 300 level and year 3 or 400 Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. Statistics shows that there are 577 Business Education students in these levels in Delta State tertiary institutions as shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Population of Business Education students in Tertiary Institutions in Delta State

S/N	Tertiary Institution	Number of Business Education
1	Delta State University, Abraka	166
2	University of Delta, Agbor	26
3	College of Education Mosogar	82
4	College of Education Warri	107
5	Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba	196
Total		577

Source: Office of the Heads of Business Education Department of the various institutions (2024)

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study adopted the simple random sampling technique to select respondents from the population. According to Nwana (1981), if a population is a few hundred, 40% or more of the population should be sampled; if in several hundreds, 20% may be sampled; and if in thousands, a sample of 10% or even less is adequate. Based on this guideline, 30% of the total population of 577 Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State was considered appropriate and randomly selected. This resulted in a sample size of 173 students.

3.4 Research Instrument

The instrument used to collect data in this study was a questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Experiential Learning, Emotional Intelligence and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition” (QELEIESA). The questionnaire contains two sections. Section A deals with the Demographic Data of the students such as gender and level of study. Section B contains rating scales made up of Experiential Learning Rating Scale, Emotional Intelligence Rating Scale and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Rating Scale. They were structured on a 4-point scale of SA (4), A (3), D (2) and SD (1) (see Appendix B, pp. 102).

3.5 Validity of Research Instrument

The questionnaire was face and content validated by three experts. Two of the experts were from Business Education Department and one expert from Guidance and Counselling Department, all from Delta State University, Abraka. In order to ensure the face and content validity of the instrument, copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the experts, who went through it and made suggestions for correction. The corrections were made before the final draft was perfected. Based on the judgement of the experts, the instrument was considered valid.

3.6 Reliability of Research Instrument

A method of internal consistency was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument. The questionnaire was administered to 50 Business Education students in University of Benin in Edo state for trial testing. The data were analysed using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient and a coefficient. This procedure examined the internal consistency of items in the instrument. It yielded the following coefficients SIWES = .79, Hands-On Training = .77, Simulation-Based Learning = .73, Self-Awareness = .76, Self-Regulation = .75, Social Skills = .81 Experiential Learning Rating Scale = .76, Emotional Intelligence Rating Scale = 0.75 and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Rating Scale = 0.78. (see Appendix C., pp.108)

3.7 Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered directly to the respondents by the researcher with the help of three (3) research assistants. The researcher went to the various public tertiary institutions offering business education in Delta State, obtain the informed consent of the students and administer the instrument on them. Salient areas in the questionnaire were explained by the researcher verbally for proper understanding. The instrument were retrieved immediately.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The data obtained were analysed with Pearson’s coefficient of determination to answer the research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and, multiple linear regression were used

to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26 used to analyse the data.

The decision rule that will be used to determine the strength of the relationship as raised in the research questions, the benchmark suggested by Cohen was adopted. Cohen (1988) suggested the following guidelines for the interpretation of the strength of relationship:

- r = .10 to .29 - Small Positive Relationship
- r = -.10 to -.29 - Small Negative Relationship
- r = .30 to .49 - Medium Positive Relationship
- r = -.30 to -.49 - Medium Negative Relationship
- r = .50 to 1.0 - High Positive Relationship
- r = -.50 to -1.0 - High Negative Relationship

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The findings of the study are tabulated as follows:

Research Questions 1: *What is the relationship between SIWES and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.1: Pearson correlation coefficient and determination of the relationship between SIWES entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students

Variable	N	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
SIWES	173	.572	.327	32.7	High positive relationship
Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition					

Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4.1 shows r-value of 0.572 which indicated high positive relationship between SIWES and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.327 and it indicates that SIWES account for 32.7% of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research Questions 2: *What is the relationship between hands-on training and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.2: Pearson correlation coefficient and determination of the relationship between hands-on training and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students

Variable	N	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Hands-On Training	173	.442	.195	19.5	Medium positive relationship
Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition					

Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4.2 indicates r-value of 0.442 which showed a medium positive relationship between hands-on training and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.195 and it indicates that hands-on training account for 19.5% of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research Questions 3: *What is the relationship between simulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.3: Pearson correlation coefficient and determination of the relationship between Simulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students

Variable	N	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Simulation	173	.435	.189	18.9	Medium positive relationship
Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition					

Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4.3 reveals the r-value of 0.435 which disclosed a medium positive relationship between simulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.189 and it indicates that simulation account for 18.9% of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research Questions 4: *What is the relationship between self-awareness and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.4: Pearson correlation coefficient and determination of the relationship between self-awareness and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students

Variable	N	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Self-awareness	173	.477	.228	22.8	Medium positive relationship
Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition					

Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4.4 reveals the r-value of 0.477 as a medium positive relationship between self-awareness and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.228 and it indicates that self-awareness account for 22.8% of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research Questions 5: *What is the relationship between self-regulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.5: Pearson correlation coefficient and determination of the relationship between self-regulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students

Variable	N	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Self-regulation	173	.461	.212	21.3	Medium positive relationship
Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition					

Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4.5 reveals the r-value of 0.461 as a medium positive relationship between self-regulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination

(r^2) is 0.212 and it displays that self-regulation account for 21.3% of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research Questions 6: *What is the relationship between social skills and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.6: Pearson correlation coefficient and determination of the relationship between social skills and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students

Variable	N	r	r^2	$r^2\%$	Decision
Social Skills	173	.541	.293	29.3	High positive relationship
Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition					

Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4.6 reveals the r-value of 0.541 as a high positive relationship between social skills and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.293 and it displays that social skills account for 29.3% of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education Students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result from research question one showed that there was a high positive relationship between SIWES and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This indicates that SIWES assist business education students to acquire entrepreneurial skills that may eventually make them to become entrepreneurs. This finding corroborate the findings of Oladokun and Oluwafemi (2015) who found that SIWES assist students to develop a competence to open their personal firm, possess negotiation skills, and exposure to their eventual working environment. Also the findings agree with that of Ojokuku , et al., (2015); Akpojotor (2023) who found that SIWES influence students positively in their professional development and that it exposed them to new work techniques and offers them opportunities for technical skill development and that students gained adequate practical experience during this training period. The study also corroborate that of Idibia et al. (2022) that students of technical and vocational education acquired relevant industrial and automobile air-conditioning skills to a high extent during SIWES for entrepreneurship development in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

The result of research question two showed that there was a medium positive relationship between hands-on training and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. This implies that hands-on training help business education students to acquire entrepreneurial skills that will make them to eventually become entrepreneurs. This finding harmonized that of Okafor (2021) that hands-on training provides students with practical experience in entrepreneurial mind-set, including traits such as creativity, innovation, risk-taking, and adaptability. Also, the finding is in agreement with that of Huang and Jiang, (2021); Lantu et al., (2022) who found in their studies that experiential learning is an important contributor to empowering students with real-world skills for future employment. Further, the study's finding agree with Ekwueme et al. (2015) that activity oriented task can instil interest of the students in learning of mathematics and Basic Science. Further, the finding supported Abdulkarim (2019) that entrepreneurial skills can be highly acquired by Business education students when action-based experiential approach is used for entrepreneurship education than when direct instruction approach is used.

The result of research question three revealed that there was a medium positive relationship between simulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students in tertiary

institutions in Delta State. This finding insinuates that simulation help business education students to acquire entrepreneurial skills that they require to become entrepreneurs in the future. This finding concurred with that of Jiafang et al. (2014) who found that simulation-based learning offered specified advantages in terms of creating active, engaging and productive environments for learning management subjects. Also, the finding is in line with Elkington et al. (2022) who affirmed that simulation helps to create a low-risk learning environment to facilitate acquisition of complex skills. In addition, the finding is in agreement with bell et al., (2008 in Jiafang, et al., 2014) that a well-designed computer simulations create a form of virtual reality that allows students to learn, apply, and refine job relevant knowledge and skills.

The result of research question four showed that there was a medium positive relationship between self-awareness and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. This shows that self-awareness is a necessary requirement for students to acquire entrepreneurial skills. This findings supported that of Atuma and Agwu (2015) that self-awareness is positively related to net profit and return on investment. Also, the finding is in conformity with Bigos and Michalik (2020) who discovered that there is a significant correlation between self-awareness and self-motivation and the students' entrepreneurial intentions.

The result of research question five revealed that there was a medium positive relationship between self-regulation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. This signifies that self-regulation is a necessary requirement for business students to acquire entrepreneurial skills. This finding is in conformity with that of Uruemunigho (2020) that self-regulation enables students to set and achieve goals, which is a critical skill for entrepreneurs who need to set and work towards business objectives. This study is in contradiction of that of Bigos and Michalik (2020) who found that there was no statistically significant influence of self-regulation, empathy, and social skills on the formation of these entrepreneurial intentions.

The result of research question six indicated a high positive relationship between social skills and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Business Education students. This implies that business students' needs social skills to acquire entrepreneurial skills. This findings is in accord with that of Khoirunikmah et al. (2022) who found that there was a positive and significant relationship between social skills and emotional intelligence and the learning achievement of students in grades IV, V, AND VI (AB). Also, the finding concord with that of Bigos and Michalik (2020) who affirmed that effective communication helps students articulate their business ideas negotiate with investors, and build strong relationships with customers and team members.

The test of hypothesis one revealed that there was a significant relationship between experiential learning and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This finding is supported by Rahim, et al. (2022) who found that teaching about entrepreneurship through case study immersion is effective to develop the cognitive ability of non-business students to recognize opportunity. In addition, the finding agreed with Lantu et al. (2022) who found that experiential learning improved the effectiveness of entrepreneurial skills training because the students experienced working in a real business setting. Furthermore, the finding concord with that of Sam and Van der Sijde (2014) who suggests that workplace-based learning has a huge contribution to Vocational Education and Training programmes because it helps students acquire job-related skills in the context in which they will be utilized in the workplace. Again, the finding is in harmony with Abdullah et al. (2019) who found that the use of experiential learning in Vocational Education and Training empowered students to acquire skills. The test of hypothesis two revealed that there was a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This implied that emotional intelligence has a significant relationship with entrepreneurial skills acquisition. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Nwibe and Ogbuanya (2024) who found that emotional intelligence had a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial intention in isolation. Further, the finding is in agreement with that of Kashif, et al. (2016) who discovered that there was a meaningful and positive relationship between entrepreneurship and all five dimensions of emotional intelligence, including

intrapersonal, interpersonal, mood, impulse control and compatibility. Also, Wen, et al. (2020) found significant positive correlation between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and emotional intelligence. While Kurjono and Saripudin (2020) found in their study that entrepreneurship learning and emotional intelligence have a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions.

The findings of hypothesis three revealed that emotional intelligence is a better predictor of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State than experiential learning. This indicated that business education students needs to possess emotional intelligence such as self-awareness, self-regulation and social skills in order for them to acquire entrepreneurial skill. This findings is in consonant with the findings of Oroka and Igberaharha (2024) who found that entrepreneurship education was a predictor of communication skills acquisition among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that SIWES and social skills have a high positive relationship with entrepreneurial skills acquisition while hands-on training, simulation, self-awareness, and self-regulation have a medium positive relationship with entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The study also concluded that emotional intelligence is a better predictor of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State than experiential learning.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation were made:

1. University management should ensure that SIWES training remain a mandatory component of university education.
2. Business education lecturers should ensure that students are engaged in hands-on training and ensure that marks are awarded to students in such trainings to encourage students to fully participate in such programmes.
3. Stakeholders of the institutions should ensure that they provide business education department with a well-furnished model office that will serve as a training ground for the students to understand how an office function in the real world.
4. Business education students should endeavour to develop their emotional intelligence quotient such as self-awareness, self-regulation and social skills as it helps in acquisition of entrepreneurial skills among students.

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